

CHARACTERIZATION OF MODE I, MODE II AND MIXED MODE I+II DELAMINATION FAILURE IN MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES FOR GLASS/EPOXY

X.J. GONG*, M.L.BENZEGGAGH*, A. LAKSIMI*, J.M.ROELANDT**

* Division Polymères et Composites

** Division Modélisation Numérique en Mécanique
UNIVERSITE DE TECHNOLOGIE DE COMPIEGNE
B.P. 649-60206 COMPIEGNE CEDEX, FRANCE

ABSTRACT

In this paper, mode I (DCB), mode II (ENF) and mixed mode I+II (MMF) delamination processes were described in multidirectional reinforced composite of glass/epoxy. By changing the reinforced angle, and keeping the symmetrical laminate properties, the effects of the laminate coupling coefficients on the critical strain energy release rate were observed. It was indicated that for the mode I dominant interlaminar fracture, the material toughness varied with the laminate coupling curvatures K_y/K_x and K_{xy}/K_x . An empirical criterion could characterize well this type of fracture. But in the case of shearing mode delamination, the mechanisms of the fracture were very different from the peeling mode dominant ones. It would be possible to exist an another fracture parameter more significant than G_{IIc} for characterizing shearing delamination.

KEY WORDS: GLASS/EPOXY; MODE I; MODE II; MIXED MODE; ENERGY RELEASE RATE; FAILURE INTERLAMINAR; MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATE

INTRODUCTION

Until present, the delamination tests under bending condition have been usually performed on unidirectional 0° composite specimens to determine interlaminar fracture resistance [1-6]. In reality, the fiber reinforced composite structures commonly used in industries are designed with the lay-ups of the type $[\pm\theta]$. The initial defects from the manufacture process can be located anywhere in a multidirectional laminate, and during loading these defects can propagate to lead to a complete fracture. In this case, by lack of balance and symmetry towards the defects, the analysis of the stress and strain fields around the crack tip, as well as the fracture mechanisms become more complex than those in unidirectional composite structures.

Therefore, there are two problems which must be faced: the first one is how to determine

the interlaminar fracture parameters and then to compare them to their respective critical values in the design of angle-ply composite structures; the second is the characterization of the delamination resistance. In other words, the material critical values must be provided as criterion. In the literature, a considerable works of the theoretical and numerical analysis were aimed at the former [7-11], the successes are remarkable. However, for the latter, although several observations to the multidirectional laminates have been published, the interpretation of the results are still far from perfect [12-15]. The work presented here has been focussed on the determination of the delamination resistance. The aim is to observe the effects of laminate coupling coefficients, which depend upon the ply orientations, stacking sequence and crack location, on the fracture toughness under mode I, mode II and mixed mode I+II loadings. A previous investigation of the pure mode I delaminations resistance using the multidirectional double cantilever beam (DCB) for a glass/epoxy composite has revealed a variations of critical strain energy release rate (CSERR) G_{IC} versus the material coupling coefficients [16-17]. Hence, for the same composite we have now selected the most popular bending tests: ENF (Edge-notch-flexure) for mode II and MMF (Mixed-mode-flexure) for mixed-mode I+II delamination.

2. EXPERIMENTAL AND THE DATA REDUCTION

2.1 Laminate configurations and experimental conditions

The laminates tested in this work were stacked from 16 quasi-unidirectional plies of prepreg of E-glass fiber with M10 epoxy resin (52% vol.) to produce a sheet of 6mm thick. 5 percent of fibers were woven perpendicularly to hold the parallel fiber together and they could set a limite to the crack shifting. The crack starter was formed by inserting a Teflon film at the mid-thickness during manufacture.

Table 1 Laminate constants

N. of LAM (V/E)	1 [04]s	2 [03/90]s	3 [(±15)2]s	4 [(±30)2]s	5 [(±45)2]s	6 [(±60)2]s	7 [(±75)2]s	8 [90/03]s
Exf(GPa)	36.2	35.82	31.99	23.03	15.57	12.02	10.844	21.53
Eyf(GPa)	10.6	11.01	10.84	12.02	15.57	23.03	31.99	25.55
Gxyf(GPa)	5.6	5.6	6.709	8.95	10.08	8.95	6.709	5.6
Gxz (GPa)	3.68	3.55	3.64	3.68	3.42	3.29	3.2	3.55
Gyz(GPa)	3.16	3.29	3.2	3.16	3.42	3.55	3.64	3.29
NUxyf	0.26	0.2505	0.3466	0.4529	0.3904	0.2364	3.62	0.1085
NUyxf	0.08	0.077	0.1175	0.2364	0.3904	0.4529	0.3466	0.1288
Ky/Kx	-0.2599	-0.2507	-0.3466	-0.453	-0.3902	-0.2364	-0.1175	-0.1085
Kxy/Kx	0	0	-0.2748	-0.2499	-0.1417	-0.0677	-0.02718	0

At the beginning, in order to simplify the problem, the symmetrical arm and two identical arms with regard to the started crack were used ($B_{ij}=0$). The laminate configurations (one arm) and their material constants were listed in the table 1.

Figure 1 presents the specimen dimensions and loading arrangement. All tests were performed in an INSTRON 1186 machine on the displacement controlled rate: 2mm/min. The onset of delamination was detected simultaneously by the acoustic emissions and the response of a strain gauge placed on the crack tip. These techniques assured well the determination of the critical values P_c .

Fig.1 Specimen geometries: DCB mode I, ENF mode II, MMF mixed-mode

2.2 Mode I data reduction (DCBspecimens)

Here, we recall in brief that the mode I CSERRs G_{Ic} were determined by the compliance method:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \frac{dc}{da} \quad (1)$$

with Berry's compliance model:

$$C = \alpha a^n \quad (2)$$

where: B-width of the specimen

P_c -critical load

α , n- empirical constants of the laminate.

2.3 Mode II data reduction (ENF specimens)

Since the experimental compliance calibration of ENF specimens requires a long span for varying the initial crack lengths, it is difficult to realize for certain lower stiffness composite. For example, before the initiation of mode II delamination for the glass/epoxy composite, a non-linear behaviour has been usually observed for the current span and crack lengths. So a lot of analytical expression for the compliance and for the mode II strain energy release rate (SERR), based on beam theory or on plate theory, have been proposed [18-20]. In this study, a higher-order beam theory (HOBT) model for the ENF specimen proposed by Whitney [20] was used to calculate CSERRs G_{IIc} :

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P_c^2 \bar{a}^2}{16Ef_x B^2 h} \left[1 + \frac{1}{75\lambda^2 \bar{a}^2} (131 + 150\bar{a}) \right] \quad (3)$$

with

$$\lambda = 4 \sqrt{\frac{14}{5} \frac{G_{xz}}{Ef_x}}, \quad \bar{a} = a/h$$

The applied load at the onset of rapid fracture was employed here as the critical loading P_c . The influence of the friction has been neglected, because $a/l \approx 0.5$ was respected.

2.4 mixed-mode data reduction (MMF specimens)

In this test, at least six specimens for each configuration were carried out with varying initial crack lengths. Supposing that the MMF specimens (I+II mixed-mode) could be considered as a superposition of DCB (mode I) and ELS (Edge Loaded Sliding mode II) specimens (see Fig.2), we have used a combined model to calculate the compliances: MMF = DCB with Kanninen's model modified by Ashizawa [9] + ELS with Whitney's HOBT model [20] as follow:

Fig.3 Correlation of experimental and analytical compliances

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DCB specimens

This test has been discussed in detail in the references [16,17, 21]. Here, we repeat briefly the principal results. The mode I delamination of the multidirectional DCB specimens, in fact, was a combination of the three peeling modes. In addition to the main peeling mode, the symmetrical twisting and bending in the direction vertical to the beam axis due to the laminate coupling curvatures would influence the fracture resistance (Tab.2). An empirical criterion was

$$\delta_p = \frac{2}{E_{fx}B} \left[\bar{a}^3 + 1.92 \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{E_{fy}} \right)^{1/4} (\bar{a}^2) + 1.22 \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{E_{fy}} \right)^{1/2} \bar{a} + 0.39 \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{E_{fy}} \right)^{3/4} \right] + \frac{1}{2E_{fx}B} \left\{ \bar{L}^3 + 3 \bar{a}^3 + \frac{3}{25\lambda^2} [387 \bar{L} + 75 \bar{a} (1+\bar{a})] \right\}$$

and $C_{(MMF)} = \delta_p / P$ (4)

where

δ_p - displacement at the loading point; C- compliance;

E_{fx}, E_{fy}, G_{xz} - bending modulus;

$$\bar{a} = \frac{a}{h}; \bar{L} = \frac{L}{a}; \lambda = 4 \sqrt{\frac{14}{5} \frac{G_{xz}}{E_{fx}}}$$

Fig.2 Separation of MMF specimens into mode I and mode II components

The results C-BT from (4) were compared with the mesured compliances C-EXP in Figure 3. We noted that for the most part, the correlation was acceptable. So it was reasonable to determine mixed mode G_c by this model:

$$G_I^m = \frac{3\bar{a}^2 P_c^2}{E_{fx} B^2 h} \left[1 + 1.28 \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{E_{fy}} \right)^{1/4} \left(\frac{1}{\bar{a}} \right) + 0.407 \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{E_{fy}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{1}{\bar{a}} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$G_{II}^m = \frac{9\bar{a}^2 P_c^2}{4E_{fx} B^2 h} \left[1 + \frac{1}{\bar{a}^2 \lambda^2} (1+2\bar{a}) \right]$$

$$G_c = G_I^m + G_{II}^m \quad (5)$$

proposed as follow:

$$G_{Ic} = [1 + \alpha \left(\frac{K_y}{K_x} \right) + \beta \left(\frac{K_{xy}}{K_x} \right)^2] G_{Ic}^* \quad (6)$$

with $G_{Ic}^* = 140 \text{ (J/m}^2\text{)}$, $a = -1$, $b = 1$ for the composite tested .

Table 2 the critical strain energy release rates on mode I, modeII and mixed mode

N. of LAM (V/E)	1 [04]s	2 [03/90]s	3 [(±15)2]s	4 [(±30)2]s	5 [(±45)2]s	6 [(±60)2]s	7 [(±75)2]s	8 [90/03]s
$G_{Ic}(J/M^2)$	184.15	167.69	189.9	211.71	193.8	179.21	181.49*	159.03
$G_{IIc}(J/M^2)$	2319.0	1952.72	1442.74	1257.47	757.84	*****	*****	1429.4
$G_c(J/M^2)^o$	512,5	514,3	660,5	733,6	591,8	532,3	327.5*	478,3

^omixed mode ratio $G_{II}/G_I=41\%$

3.2 ENF specimens

The mode II CSERRs G_{IIc} are also presented in table 2. For laminates of lay-up $[(±60)_2]_s$ and $[(±75)_2]_s$, We were unable to measure G_{IIc} because specimens were broken by flexion instead of the onset of the delamination.

Compared with the values of G_{Ic} , The G_{IIc} values are much higher. It is resulted in the different micromechanisms of delamination in the epoxy matrix composite. In the case of mode I delamination, microcracks in the matrix were very localized around the crack tip. When the delamination occurred on mode II, the matrix behaved in a ductile way. G_{IIc} was thus governed by the energy dissipated in the more extensive matrix plastic deformation and damage regions around the crack tip.

Another observation on G_{IIc} values is a little surprising: G_{IIc} varied from 757,8 (J/m²) to 2319,0 (J/m²), the difference is about 3 times for the same material. For the explanation of this variation, we have tried to correct G_{IIc} with a large displacement theory [9]. But the difference between G_{IIc} for the small and great reinforced angle would be more important, because the non-linear comportement for the latter was more considerable. On the other hand, let us examined the mechanics of the crack driving force in ENF specimens.

The ENF specimens was loaded in bending, the ratio a/h of the specimens used in this work were so high as to neglect the shear force. Figure 4 shows that the dominante sliding deformation and shear stresses would be generated by the discontinuity in stress at the crack tip. They drived the shearing delaminations (mode II). Moreover since the loading condition contrained the liberal deformation at the points of two supports and at the centre of the beam, the presence of coupling curvatures K_y and K_{xy} in angle-plyed laminates would bring about an additional load M_y^* , M_{xy}^* , which gave the participation of tearing mode (mode III). In fact, the angle-plyed ENF specimens was subjected on mixed-mode II+III loading. Certainly, tearing component was not a

dominant mode, which can't give a reasonable explanations of the variation of the G_{IIc} values. Consequently, we have taken in a possibility: whether there is an another fracture parameter more significant than G_{IIc} values for multidirectional laminates mode II delamination. In order to answer this question, it seems necessary to carry out a fractographic study so as to investigate the fracture surface morphology and associate the reinforced fiber angle with the fracture energy.

Fig.3 Mechanisms of ENF specimen crack driving force

3.3 MMF specimens

As described above, The MMF specimen can be equivalently partitioned into DCB (mode I) and ELS (mode II) specimens, and so the mechanisms of crack driving force have to be a superposition of them. We know that the stress state at the crack tip of the ELS specimens is fairly the same as the ENF ones. In consequence, the delamination of this specimen is a I + II + III mixed mode. This could be verified by a 3D finite element analysis. It is interesting to note that the variation of G_c showed a tendency similar to mode I (see tab.2), for the reason of the mode I dominant crack growth for MMF specimens. Here, the G_c value for the $[(\pm 75)_2]_s$ lay-up was unsure, because of the fracture by flexion.

As a result, we propose here a criterion with the same form as (6). If the mechanism of the delamination different from that of DCB specimens (pure peeling) was recognized, the coupling terms K_y/K_x and K_{xy}/K_x would produce not only the additional peeling, such as in DCB specimens, but also the mode III component. Therefore they do have the different contribution to G_c . It means that the laminate constants α , β and G_c^* must depend on the delamination mode. By interpolating the results of G_c , we can determine empirically α , β and G_c^* for the mixed mode ratio $G_{II}/G_I=41\%$, we obtain:

$$\alpha = -0.8 \quad , \quad \beta = 4 \quad , \quad G_c^* = 430 \text{ (J / m}^2\text{)}$$

$$G_c = \left[1 - 0.8 \frac{K_y}{K_x} + 4 \left(\frac{K_{xy}}{K_x} \right)^2 \right] G_c^* \tag{7}$$

It was seen that for the MMF specimens, while the terme $\frac{K_{xy}}{K_x}$ played a role more important in G_c , the participation of the $\frac{K_y}{K_x}$ decreased. If now we draw G_c -mol given by (7) and G_c^{exp} versus the number of laminate in the figure 5, the criterion (6) seems a satisfactory approach for mode I dominant delamination. In order to establish the relation between α , β , G_c^* and mixed mode ratio G_{II}/G_T for all mode I dominant delamination, it needs yet a lot of the experimental data and the future researches.

FIG. 5 The variation of G_c for MMF specimens ($G_{II}/G_T=41\%$)

4. CONCLUSION

1. If the dominant mode of delamination is peeling, even in the case of mixed mode, the effects of laminate coupling coefficients on G_c values could be described efficiently by an empirical criterion:

$$G_c = [1 + \alpha \left(\frac{K_y}{K_x}\right) + \beta \left(\frac{K_{xy}}{K_x}\right)^2] G_c^*$$

where α , β , G_c^* are material constants, they depend on the mixed-mode ratio G_{II}/G_T .

2. The G_{IIc} values showed a great dependance of laminate lay-ups. Is there another parameter more significant than G_{IIc} to characterize the resistance to mode II crack growth? A fractographic study will be required.

5. REFERENCES

1. M.L. Benzeggagh, Y. Prel and F.X. De Charentenay, Proceedings of the 1st European Conference on Composite Materials, ECCM-I, Bordeaux, 1984, pp.291-311

2. M.L. Benzeggagh, X.J. Gong and J.M. Roelandt, Proceedings of the 7th international Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM7, Beijing, 1989, p.210
3. M.L. Benzeggagh, P. DAVIES, X.J. Gong and J.M. Roelandt, Composites Science and Technology, 34 pp124-143 (1989)
4. M.L. Benzeggagh, X.L. GONG, X.J. Gong and J.M. Roelandt, Proceedings of the 7me Journées Nationales sur Matériaux Composites, JNC7, Loyn, Nov 1990
5. P. Davies, W. Cantwell, C.Moulin & H.H. Kausch, Composites Science and Technology, 36, pp.153-166 (1989)
6. S. Hashemi, A.J. Kinloch, and J.G. Williams, J. of Composites Materials, vol. 24-Sept. p.918 (1989)
7. J.M. Whitney, Comp. Scien. and Tech., 23, pp.201-219 (1985)
8. P.L.N. Murthy and C.C. Chamis, J.DJ Whitcomb, Ed., Comp. Mate.: Testing and Design, ASTM STP 972 , 1988, pp.23-40
9. K. Friedrich Ed. Application of Fracture Mechanics to Composite Materials, Composite Materials series 6, Elsevier Science Publishers B.V. 1989
10. B.D. Davidson, J. of Comp. Mate. Vol. 24-Nov. p.1124 (1989)
11. B.D. Davidson and R.A. Schapery, J. of Comp. Mate. Vol. 22-july. p.640 (1987)
12. Marom G., Romain I, Harrel H. and Rosensatt M., Proceedings of the 6th international Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM-VI, 3, 1987, pp.65-273
13. Miller A.G., Hertzberg P.E., and Rantala V.W., 12th Nationale SAMPE Technical Conference (Octobre 7-9 1980) pp. 279-293
14. Wilkins D.J., Eisenmann J.R., Camin R.A., Margolis W.S. and Benson R.A., ASTM. STP 775 (1982) pp.168-183
15. Nicholls D.J. Gallagher J.P., J. of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, 2 pp.2-17 (January 1983)
16. X.J. Gong, M.L. Benzeggagh, A. Laksimi, J.M.Roelandt, Proceedings of the 4th European Conference on Composite Materials, ECCM-4, Stuttgart, 1990, p.163
17. X.J. Gong, M.L. Benzeggagh, A. Laksimi, J.M.Roelandt, Presented at the 9th NRCC/IMI symposium "composites-'90"
18. S. Mall and N.K. Kochhar J. of Comp. Tech. & Res. Vol.8, No.2 (Sum. 1986) pp.54-57
19. L.A. Carlsson, J.W. Gillespie JR. and R.B. Pipes, J. of Comp. Mate. Vol.20 (Nov.1986) p. 594
20. J. Whitney, M. Pinnell, Proceedings of the 4th European Conference on Composite Materials, ECCM-4, Stuttgart, 1990, p.865
21. A.Laksimi, M.L.Benzeggagh, X.J.Gong, M.Hecini, & J.M.Roelandt, Comp. Scien. and Tech. 41 pp.147-164 (1991)